

Book of Abstracts of the 74th Annual Meeting of the European Federation of Animal Science

Book of abstracts No. 29 (2023)
Lyon, France
26 August – 1 September, 2023

Gallic acid alleviates the negative effect of <i>Asparagopsis armata</i> on milk yield in dairy cows <i>R. Huang, P. Romero, C. Martin, E.M. Ungerfeld, A. Demeter, A. Belanche, D.R. Yáñez-Ruiz, M. Popova and D. Morgavi</i>	940
Milk production in primiparous cows with customized voluntary waiting period <i>A. Edvardsson Rasmussen, E. Strandberg, R. Båge, M. Åkerlind, K. Holtenius and C. Kronqvist</i>	941
Association of nisin and <i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> against <i>S. aureus</i> isolated from bovine mastitis <i>L. Castelani, T.M. Mitsunaga, L.C. Roma Jr. and L.E.F. Zadra</i>	941

Session 86. How to address stakeholder and societal expectations of intrinsic and extrinsic quality of animal products?

Date: Thursday 31 August 2023; 14.00 – 18.00

Theatre Session 86

Quick sustainability scan calculator for intensive and extensive pig farms <i>S. Sanz-Fernández, C. Reyes-Palomo, P. Meatquality Consortium and V. Rodríguez-Estévez</i>	942
Bulk milk and farms characterization in the Parmigiano Reggiano Consortium area: the INTAQT project <i>M. Berton, M.A. Ramirez Mauricio, N. Amalfitano, L. Gallo, A. Cecchinato and E. Sturaro</i>	942
Bridging environmental sustainability and intrinsic quality traits of pork <i>M. Gagaoua, F. Gondret, F. Garcia-Launay and B. Lebret</i>	943
Improving milk intrinsic quality: considering synergies and antagonisms of farming practices <i>L. Rey-Cadilhac, A. Ferlay, M. Gelé, S. Léger and C. Laurent</i>	943
Imagining futures of husbandry farming: new business models for the sustainable transition? <i>B. Smulders, R. Valkenburg and M. Anastasi</i>	944
Current prediction and authentication tools used and needed in EU livestock product chains <i>S. McLaughlin, F. Albert, F. Bedoin, C. Couzy, I. Legrand, A. Nicolazo De Barmon, C. Laithier, C. Manuelian, F. Klevenhusen, S. De Smet, E. Sturaro and N. Scollan</i>	944
Milk quality assessment for intensive and extensive goat farming of the Skopelos breed in Greece <i>Z. Basdagianni, I. Stavropoulos, G. Manessis, C.G. Biliaderis and I. Bossis</i>	945
Rheological evaluation of rennet-induced curdling of goat milks from different farming systems <i>K. Kotsiou, M. Andreadis, A. Lazaridou, C.G. Biliaderis, Z. Basdagianni, I. Bossis and T. Moschakis</i>	945
invited Technological tools for authentication assessment of animal products <i>C.L. Manuelian</i>	946
Potential of milk infrared spectroscopy to discriminate farm characteristics: the INTAQT project <i>M.A. Ramirez Mauricio, D. Giannuzzi, L. Gallo, M. Berton, A. Cecchinato and E. Sturaro</i>	946
A longitudinal cohort study of health and welfare status in extensively and intensively reared goats <i>V. Korelidou, A.I. Kalogianni and A.I. Gelasakis</i>	947
New tool for accurate analysis of gas concentrations in barns <i>O. Bonilla-Manrique, A. Moreno-Oyervides, H. Moser, J.P. Waclawek, B. Lendl and P. Martín-Mateos</i>	947

Milk quality assessment for intensive and extensive goat farming of the Skopelos breed in Greece**Z. Basdagianni¹, I. Stavropoulos¹, G. Manassis¹, C.G. Biliaderis² and I. Bossis¹**¹Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Animal Production, School of Agriculture, Thessaloniki, 54124, Greece,²Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Food Science and Technology, School of Agriculture, Thessaloniki, 54124, Greece; basdagianni@agro.auth.gr

The objective of the study was to evaluate the quality of goat milk produced in an intensive (I) and an extensive (E) farming system throughout the lactation period in the Greek Skopelos dairy goats. 938 individual milk samples from 235 goats (105 and 135, for the intensive and the extensive system respectively) were collected at 4 different lactation stages starting immediately after weaning. Milk composition (fat, protein, lactose, and total solids content), physicochemical characteristics (pH, electrical conductivity, brix value, and refractive index), fatty acid composition, somatic cells count (SCC) and total bacterial count (TBC) were measured. A mixed linear model was used to determine the effects ($P \leq 0.01$) of farming system, and lactation stage on the milk quality assessment parameters. The farming system had no significant effect on the chemical composition and physicochemical properties of milk. Farming system however, significantly affected ($P \leq 0.01$) SCC (509.02 vs 841.29 cell/ml $\times 1000$, for the I and E, respectively) and TBC (21.49 vs E:326.45 cfu $\times 1000$ for the I and E, respectively). In addition, farming system affected certain parameters of FA composition. Total unsaturated FAs were higher ($P \leq 0.01$) in the E system (27.39%) compared to the I system (21.99%). More specifically, polyunsaturated fatty acids were 3.58 and 4.24% and monounsaturated FAs were 18.41 and 23.15% for the I and the E systems, respectively. Differences in SCC and TBC between the two farming systems are probably due to milking practices and overall hygiene status. In contrast, the superior lipid profile in the extensive farming system could probably be attributed to grazing for the majority of the lactation period. This work was funded by EU (HORIZON H2020) under the 'Code Re-farm: Consumer-driven demands to reframe farming systems' (Grant No: 101000216).

Session 86

Theatre 8

Rheological evaluation of rennet-induced curdling of goat milks from different farming systems**K. Kotsiou¹, M. Andreadis¹, A. Lazaridou¹, C.G. Biliaderis¹, Z. Basdagianni², I. Bossis² and T. Moschakis¹**¹Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Food Science and Technology, Thessaloniki, 541 24, Greece, ²Aristotle

University of Thessaloniki, Department of Animal Production, School of Agriculture, Thessaloniki, 541 24, Greece; basdagianni@agro.auth.gr

The present study focuses on the rheological assessment of rennet-induced coagulation of milk from dairy goats of the Greek Skopelos breed. The goats were raised by either an extensive or an intensive farming system at two separate farms in Greece. The milk samples were collected after weaning. Dynamic rheological measurements were used to assess the kinetics of milk coagulation at 35 °C following the addition of rennet as well as the mechanical properties of the formed coagulum (cheese curds). The rennet coagulation time (defined as the time of the abrupt increase of storage modulus, G') of the milk samples from the extensive goat farming system was shorter than that for samples of the intensive farming system, without affecting the curd firming rate, determined by the increment of elasticity ($IE = (d \log G' / dt)_{max}$), a parameter used as a measure of the gelation rate. Curds obtained from goat milks raised by the extensive farming system exhibited higher G' at 35 °C and complex viscosity (η^*) values, compared to those of the intensive system; i.e. stronger gel network structures were noted for the extensive farming system samples. The observed differences in the rheological behaviour may be ascribed mainly to differences in the compositional and/or structural characteristics of the protein components (e.g. casein fractions) content between the two groups of samples. The rheological findings make an interesting contribution to the field of animal science and cheesemaking, by demonstrating how the goat feeding system may affect the mechanical properties of rennet-coagulated cheese products. This work was funded by EU (HORIZON H2020) under the 'Code Re-farm: Consumer-driven demands to reframe farming systems' (Grant No: 101000216).